

Traditional practices and resource management among the Karbi tribe with reference to Karbis of Dimoria under Kamrup Metro district of Assam

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Abstract: The Karbi tribe is one of the major ethnic groups in northeast India, belonging to the Tibeto-Burman linguistic family, and is among the oldest inhabitants of Assam. The Karbis living in the plains of Assam are referred to as *dumrali* or plain Karbis. They are known to have a high sense of reverence and pride towards their aspect of inherent masculinity. The word Karbi signifies a sense of brotherhood. The Karbi tribe, indigenous to Kamrup Metro in Assam, India offers a wealth of traditional knowledge and practices in sustainable resource management, which have been integral to their way of life for generations. The Karbis of the Dimoria region live alongside and coexist with various other communities. This paper explores how the Karbi indigenous practices, deeply rooted in their cultural and spiritual beliefs, promote environmental conservation and sustainable use of natural resources. Their shifting cultivation (*jhum*), community-based forest management and water conservation techniques demonstrate a profound understanding of ecological balance. These practices not only maintain biodiversity but also ensure the sustainability of resources for future generations. By blending traditional ecological knowledge with modern sustainability initiatives, the Karbi tribe's practices provide valuable insights into managing natural resources in a manner that is both environmentally sustainable and culturally respectful.

Keywords: Karbi, Traditional Knowledge, Practices, Sustainability, Resource Management

Introduction:

The Karbis are a tribal community in Assam, formerly referred to as 'Mikirs.' However, the indigenous members of the community prefer the term 'arlung,' which translates to a Mikir man. The history regarding the origin of Karbis is not clear even today and even their ancestors had forgotten their origins (Engtipi and Dhanaraju, 2020). They rarely remained in one place for an extended period, as they primarily practiced shifting cultivation. When the land began to lose its fertility, they would abandon it and relocate to cultivate a new area. The Karbis living in the plains of Assam are commonly known as *dumrali* or plain Karbis. They are known to have a high sense of reverence and pride towards their aspect of inherent masculinity. According to Sarma (2021), the term *Karbi* embodies the concept of brotherhood. The Karbis reject the label 'Mikirs' as they consider it derogatory and imposed by outsiders (Das et al., 2020). Sustainable resource management refers to the responsible and efficient use of natural resources to meet current needs while ensuring their availability for future generations. This approach balances environmental, economic and social factors to promote long-term stability and prevent the depletion or degradation of essential resources like water, soil, forests, and minerals.

Traditional knowledge and practices are the time-honored systems of understanding and methods cultivated by indigenous communities over generations, shaped through their continuous interaction with the surrounding environment (Engtipi & Dhanaraju, 2020). This knowledge is all-encompassing, covering a wide range of cultural beliefs, practices, skills, and understandings related to the management of natural resources, healthcare, agriculture, education, and social structures (Rist & Dahdouh-Guebas, 2006). Unlike formal scientific knowledge, traditional knowledge is often passed down orally, through practices, folklore, stories, and rituals, and stories rather than through written records (Kelly, 2015). Traditional practices see humans, nature and the spiritual world as interconnected. For example, many indigenous beliefs involve respecting the land and practicing conservation because natural resources are considered sacred (Ormsby & Bhagwat, 2010). It has increasingly gained recognition for their role in sustainable development, biodiversity conservation, and climate resilience, offering alternative solutions to many modern environmental challenges (Ramakrishnan, 2003).

This paper is an attempt to highlight the traditional practices and resource management among the Karbi tribe of Dimoria region of Kamrup Metro district of Assam. While several studies have focused on the Karbis living in Karbi Anglong, there is a lack of comprehensive research on the traditional practices and resource management among the Karbi tribe in the Dimoria region. The paper tries to analyze and emphasize the sustainability aspects of Karbi traditional practices in the Kamrup Metro District.

Study Area: Kamrup Metro district lies between latitudes 25°43' and 26°51' North and longitudes 90°36' and 92°12' East. It is bounded by Kamrup district on the north and west, Morigaon district to the east, and the state of Meghalaya to the south.

Methodology: In the present study, empirical methodology has been used. It refers to a research approach that relies on observed and measured phenomena to gather data and generate knowledge. Data were collected from both primary and secondary sources. Primary data was obtained through field visits, interviews, and observations, while secondary data was gathered from books, journals, souvenirs, and other related materials.

Dimoria: Dimoria is the homeland of ethnic groups like Karbi, Bodo, Tiwa, Garos and many non-tribal Assamese people. The Dimoria region serves as a convergence point for a diverse mix of tribes, sub-tribes, castes and communities. As per the 2011 Census, tribal communities constitute 16.40% of the population in this area. Prominent among these are the Karbi, Tiwa, Bodo, Rabha, Deori, and Garo communities (Devee, 2023). Additionally, Dimoria's close proximity to Guwahati—the leading educational, commercial, and industrial hub of Assam and the entire North-Eastern region—places it within the city's sphere of influence.

About the tribe Karbi:

The Karbi tribe is regarded as one of the prominent ethnic communities in Assam. It is the third largest tribe in Assam after Boro and Mishing. The etymology of the word *Karbi* is traced to the term *thakarkabi*, which refers to the offering of sacrifices at the beginning of religious rituals, such as worshipping God or during marriage ceremonies, the birth of a child, or harvesting of crops, known as Thakar Kibi. The word eventually evolved into "Karbi" by omitting the syllables 'tha' and 'ki' (Sarma, 2021). Major section of the community is living in the district of Karbi Anglong, a hill district of Assam, however, Karbi settlements are also found in several other districts like Nagaon, Morigaon, Kamrup, Sonitpur, Golaghat, Sibsagar, Lakhimpur and North Cachar Hills district of Assam (Engtipi & Dhanaraju, 2020).

Some of traditional practices of the tribe:

Agricultural Practices: The Dimoria region is rich in agriculture which incorporates multiple crops and plants for food security, soil enrichment, and resilience against climate variations. The average annual temperature is around 27° C, and the average annual rainfall is about 200 cm. The winters in this region are generally mild, with temperatures ranging from 6-7° C. The monsoon season, which

typically lasts from June to September/October, brings the majority of the rainfall (Bhuyan & Sharma, 2017). Due to its sub-tropical monsoon climate, characterized by heavy rainfall and warm temperatures the Dimoria region has plentiful of agricultural productions. Orange, pineapple, ginger, turmeric and other vegetables from Dimoria are famous in the whole nation (Singh et al., 2017).

Jhum Cultivation (Shifting Agriculture): The Karbi of Kamrup (M) district that lives near the hilly areas or in hilly slopes practices jhum or shifting cultivation (Bhagawati, 2024). It is a traditional form of agriculture where a patch of land is cleared, cultivated for a few years and then left fallow to restore its fertility (Meetei & Tsopoe, 2024). This practice, although criticized in modern times, is managed sustainably by the Karbis through rotational cycles, allowing the forest to regenerate. Shifting cultivation is often deeply rooted in indigenous cultures and traditions and there is a significant socio-cultural aspect of Jhum cultivation in the Karbi society (Bhagawati, 2024). In this type of farming, human labour is the main factor needed to keep the activity going, rather than using animals for ploughing and this type of practice is a part of community's cultural life. This shifting cultivation method provides the advantages such as firewood, house building materials and timber to the nearby Karbi population (Bhagawati, 2024).

Rituals and Festivals linked to Agriculture: Festivals like Rongker and Chojunare essential to Karbi agricultural life. 'Rongker' is a community worship ritual aimed at seeking blessings from deities for good harvests and environmental protection (Rongpi, 2024). These festivals reinforce the importance of sustainable agricultural practices and respect for nature (Engtipi & Dhanaraju, 2020). 'Dehal Katsirdom' is a significant community worship of the Karbis of Dimoria region and is considered as a symbol of unity and togetherness among the Karbis. Ankimi Kitso is a post-harvest celebration that combines both feasting and worship. It is an occasion for joy and gratitude, offered in honor of the 'God of Agriculture' (Barua & Kikhi, 2016).

Traditional Hunting and Fishing Practices: Hunting and fishing are important aspects of Karbi culture. However, these activities are carried out with respect for ecological balance. The Karbi of Kamrup (Metro) district follow seasonal hunting rules, allowing species to replenish, and use traditional fishing methods that minimize harm to aquatic ecosystems, like net, bamboo traps etc (Hansepi & Laisram, 2022). Community fishing is practised every year on the day of uruka in the month of January (Rongpi, 2024). In many Karbi villages the villagers prepare a temporary house with straw, bamboo and dry banana leaves where they performed their traditional culture followed by community feast. There is one tradition amongst the karbi tribe to kill the birds and offers it to the village headman (Sharma, 2016; Dhanaraju & Bijeta, 2024).

Traditional Karbi culinary practices: Culinary traditions serve as strong markers of cultural identity, with food, culture, and identity being closely interconnected. Moreover, food plays a vital role in reflecting a community's socialization patterns. Among the Karbis of the Dimoria region, everyday meals, festive food customs, and traditional kitchen practices are deeply rooted in their cultural heritage. These longstanding culinary traditions are intricately woven into the social fabric of the community (Barua & Kikhi, 2016). One of the notable items is rice beer, commonly referred to as 'hor' by the Karbis. The staple food of Karbis is rice. The diet of the Karbi community is largely shaped by the locally available plants, animals, and agricultural produce of their region. Their cuisine features several traditional and distinctive food items, each prepared using unique indigenous methods. Some examples include: i) Kang-Moi (Alkaline): This is made by extracting alkaline from the ashes of dried banana stems. ii) Sukan Mas / Fermented Fish (Dry Fish): The preparation involves drying the fish with salt, applying crushed turmeric, and then sealing it inside a locally sourced bamboo tube. The fish is left to ferment for two to five months. iii) Gaaj (bamboo shoot): Like the other tribal groups of the region, bamboo shoot is one of the most favourite ingredients in Amri Karbi cuisine (Barua, & Kikhi, 2016). The Karbis have a unique style of fermenting and storing bamboo shoot to prepare delicacy items. The tender shoots of the bamboos are collected, cleaned, cut into small pieces and then stored in bamboo tubes for fermentation (Nongdam & Tikendra, 2014). Once fermented, the bamboo shoot is used in various dishes, often cooked with dried or fresh fish and meat, and at times, served as a pickle during meals.

iv) **Dry Meat:** The Karbi community traditionally preserves different types of meat—such as wild pig, domesticated pig, goat, and deer—by drying them. Before consumption, the dried meat is soaked in water and then either boiled or cooked. Additionally, **betel-nut and betel leaves** hold an important place in Karbi dietary habits. Among Karbis in the plains, chewing betel-nut after meals and during special occasions is a widely observed custom.

The tradition of working together by the Karbi community members for a Karbi home (Howri): The Karbi community practices the tradition of working together by its community members for their families which is known as *howri* (Rongpi, 2024). This work is mostly performed by the group members with a helping attitude in their minds where they do not charge any wages. This tradition reduces financial burden as well as strengthen the community bond to each other. The youth, elders and women’s gradually develops mentality to provide community service through the groups in the name of *howri* tradition (Sharma, 2016).

Traditional medicinal Plant usage: The Karbis of Kamrup (M) district possess extensive traditional knowledge about the medicinal properties of local plants and herbs. They use these plants to treat various ailments, which has been passed down through generations. This knowledge helps them maintain a healthy balance between their needs and environmental preservation. Borthakur & Goswami (1994) on their research on herbal remedies from Dimoria of Kamrup district of Assam had reported forty-two empirically accepted prescriptions for 38 ailments, involving 27 plant species with details of prescribed doses and administration.

Traditional Handicrafts: The Karbi tribe is known for its handicrafts, particularly weaving and bamboo crafts. The production process emphasizes sustainable use of locally sourced natural materials like bamboo, cotton, and other fibres, maintaining ecological balance (Teron & Borthakur, 2012; Das et al., 2021). Among the Karbi community, bamboo stands out as one of the most widely utilized plant resources. It is a highly versatile plant that plays a crucial role in supporting ecological balance, economic activities, and livelihood security for the people of India’s northeastern states (Singha & Timung, 2015). There is a popular Karbi proverb prevalent in the community about the significant dependence of the Karbis on bamboo resources. Han-up or bamboo shoots is a major source of food during scarcity of rice; a traditional festival is celebrated to mark the bamboo shoots harvesting season (Teron & Borthakur, 2012). The Karbi community also follows specific taboos and cultural restrictions regarding the use of bamboo. Bamboo also holds significant potential for enhancing the rural economy of the Karbi community (Borthakur et al., 2021).

Traditional Forest Management: Karbis of Kamrup (M) district have indigenous knowledge of forest management and utilize a range of forest resources for food, medicine and shelter while maintaining ecological sustainability (Mipun et al., 2019). They follow community rules about resource extraction, ensuring the forests remain healthy and productive (Das et al., 2024). The Karbi community tries their best to sustain both ecological balance and cultural identity, for a sustainable resource management and the tribe’s connection to the environment (Mipun et al., 2019; Das et al., 2024).

Community-based water conservation: Karbi villages of Kamrup (M) district often have traditional systems of water management, such as small check dams and ponds, to conserve rainwater (Das et al., 2024). These help in maintaining the water table and ensuring availability of water for agriculture and daily use throughout the year. The traditional methods such as managing human-made canals (*dongs*) and ponds, organic farming, and biodiversity conservation practices demonstrate a holistic approach to maintaining ecological balance and the Karbi cultural heritage (Das et al., 2024).

Community land ownership: Community land ownership involves the collective possession and stewardship of land by a community or group, as opposed to individual or corporate ownership. This practice of common land ownership is followed in the Karbi community (Engtipi & Dhanaraju, 2020). This model empowers communities by giving them control over how the land is used and maintained, ensuring that the benefits from the land are distributed among its members (Borthakur, 2023). It is often aimed at promoting social, economic, and environmental sustainability. Collective ownership of

land and its impact on sustainable use and conservation, fostering a sense of responsibility among community members (Engtipi & Dhanaraju, 2020).

The traditional practices of the Karbi tribe in Assam offer valuable insights and advantages in sustainable resource management that can benefit all communities in the region. These practices blend ecological wisdom, cultural heritage and sustainable techniques that contribute to a balanced use of natural resources. Agricultural Practices and land management techniques can be adapted by other communities to promote agro-ecological farming and maintain soil quality, contributing to food security and environmental conservation. Other communities can learn to implement seasonal and size-selective fishing methods to maintain healthy fish stocks and ensure long-term livelihoods for those dependent on fishing. Sharing traditional culinary practices, medicinal plant knowledge can help other communities use local flora for health purposes, diversify healthcare options and promote the conservation of plant biodiversity. Communities can incorporate similar sustainable crafting practices of Karbi community to develop local industries that support livelihoods, promote cultural heritage and reduce environmental impact. Other communities can benefit from water conservation practices of the community by implementing rainwater harvesting and natural filtration systems to enhance water security and sustainability. Further, the collective ownership of land and its impact on sustainable use and conservation will foster a sense of responsibility among community members.

Challenges to Karbi traditional practices

With the current age of modernization and urbanization, the Karbis settled in the places nearby places of Guwahati city poses various threat and challenges toward the practice of traditional norms and culture. Certain culinary traditions and practices have been discontinued as a result of adaptation and integration between internal community dynamics and external cultural influences. The lack of resource centres and a decline in Traditional Knowledge Transmission to propagate, conserve and document the Karbi culture, traditions and language have posed a threat to the future of Karbi cultural traditions. Encroachment and Resource Competition have also been amongst the challenges to Karbi traditional practices. Further, the lack of efficient Government policies and support for Indigenous Resource Management for the Karbi community of the region is a hindrance for the prosperity of the Karbi traditional practices.

Conclusion:

The Karbi tribe of the Dimoria region in Assam exemplifies a harmonious relationship between culture, environment, and community through their rich traditional knowledge and sustainable practices. Their indigenous methods—ranging from jhum cultivation and forest management to water conservation, culinary traditions, and medicinal plant use—reflect a deep understanding of ecological balance and cultural continuity. These practices not only support the tribe's livelihoods and reinforce communal identity but also offer viable, eco-friendly alternatives to modern resource management challenges. However, the encroachment of modernization, weakening intergenerational knowledge transfer, and inadequate policy support pose significant threats to the preservation of Karbi traditions. Recognizing, respecting, and integrating these indigenous systems into broader sustainability frameworks is essential—not only for the Karbi community's resilience but also for the global pursuit of environmentally and culturally sustainable development.

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